

IMPROVEMENT OF AUTUMN WHEAT FEEDING AND CADASTRE PLACEMENT IN THE ARAL SEA REGION

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Abstract

Due to the low fertility of the soil in Karakalpakstan and the fact that groundwater is close to the surface, attention should be paid to the correct application of fertilizers and the cadastral placement of winter wheat.

Keywords: Aral Sea, Karakalpakstan, winter wheat, fertilization, cadastral setting, saline soils, extreme climate, low water;

Introduction. The technology of wheat cultivation in the conditions of saline soils and unfavorable climate change and water scarcity of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is a unique feature of this region. According to statistics, today the total grain grown in the world is about 650 million tons, of which 50% is accounted for by fertilizers. For example, according to the Research Institute of Fertilizers and Soil Science named after DN Pryanishnikov, among all factors in the structure of the crop fertilizer contributes 40-50%, agro-technical measures 20-30%, and variety 20%.

A method of studying the problem. During the study of the experiment, the field method was used, and in mathematical and statistical processing the method of B.A. Dospekhov was used.

The results of the experiment. The winter wheat fertilization system includes the use of organic fertilizers, mineral fertilizers and chemical ameliorants. In our experiment on alluvial soils of the meadow of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, winter wheat averaged 30-35kg per 1 ton of grain. nitrogen, 15-25 kg. 25-27 kg of mobile phosphorus and potassium were assimilated. In the experiment, the main fertilizer under the winter wheat fertilization system was applied to the soil before the main tillage. In addition, wheat was fed during the operation. In this case, the annual rate of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers was applied before the main tillage. The main fertilizer given to winter wheat is

to meet the plant's need for nutrients throughout the application period. When nutrients are not enough, it is necessary to create sufficient conditions for the autumn harvest of wheat and the formation of productive generative organs.

From the results of our experiments, the fact that the annual norms of the main types of fertilizers applied to winter wheat are set in relation to the planned yield has given a positive result. In this case, in determining the amount of fertilizer should be taken into account the amount of nutrients in the soil reserves assimilated by the plant and the amount of nutrients assimilated in the given fertilizer. The amount of fertilizer applied depends not only on the amount of nutrients in the soil, but also on the climatic conditions of the soil and the level of agrotechnology.

In addition, it is known from our experience that timely application of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers also increased the resistance of plants to cold, fungal and bacterial diseases, bed bugs. If for some reason the soil is not given phosphorus and potassium fertilizers before the main tillage, it can be given before planting or in conjunction with planting. Nitrogen fertilizers were applied in a stratified manner in autumn, early spring, at the beginning of the harvesting phase and in the germination phases during the application period to winter wheat. If winter wheat is planted in areas with low soil fertility, 20-30% of nitrogen fertilizers should be applied before preparing the soil for planting, and the rest should be applied during the application period. If winter wheat is planted in areas with low soil fertility, 20-30% of nitrogen fertilizers should be applied before preparing the soil for planting, and the rest should be applied during the application period. In fertile soil conditions, wheat plant growth and development is good, with 3-4 stems in each round, spring nitrogen fertilization in the first place in areas that have entered the dormant period and well out of winter at the rate of 40-50% of the annual norm of nitrogen fertilizer (50-60 kg per hectare). at the expense of the active substance) at the end of the accumulation phase and at the beginning of the piping phase.

According to the results of our research, during the period of application of winter wheat, the second nitrogen feeding gave a positive result of 30-50% of the annual norm of nitrogen in the full tube phase (40-50 kg of active substance per hectare). Also, the implementation of the third nitrogen feeding of wheat in the initial phase of wheat during the application period increased grain quality by 20-22% and yield by 7-9%.

For some reason, in areas where wheat is not planted in autumn nitrogen feeding, nitrate content in the soil in early spring is very low. The reason is that

the nutrients accumulated by the plant are consumed by the plant during the winter. Therefore, nitrogen deficiency was observed in the plant in early spring. In our experiment, nitrogen feeding of winter wheat in early spring rapidly grew the root system and blue mass of plants, enlarged the spike, increased the number of spikes, which in turn laid the groundwork for the planned harvest.

In the experiment to improve the cadastral location of wheat, mainly in the experiment on the relief and groundwater location on the surface, groundwater - groundwater is located at a depth of 1-1.5 m, 1.5-2 m, 2.5-3.0 m and deeper, and The experiment was conducted on low, medium and high terrain. According to the results, groundwater at a depth of 1-1.5 meters, in low-altitude soils in the early spring due to the rise of groundwater, autumn wheat seedlings died by 67-74%. In places where groundwater is located at a depth of 1.5-2.0 meters and the average height, the loss of seedlings was observed in the range of 12-34%, depending on the mechanical composition of the soil. No sapling loss was observed in the areas where the groundwater depth is 2.5-3.0 meters and above and the relief is high. This means that if possible, the farm should plant groundwater at a depth of 2.5-3.0 meters or more and in areas with high relief to protect the autumn wheat seedlings from autumn-winter and early spring losses and to obtain the planned harvest.

Conclusions and recommendations.

1. In early spring feeding is recommended to give 25 percent of nitrogen fertilizers at the expense of the substance that affects the annual rate.

2. Nitrogen feeding in early spring is recommended to be carried out first in the areas that have come out of the winter with difficulty, then in the areas sown for seed production and in all other areas.

3. Early spring feeding stabilized seedling thickness and accelerated the process of accumulation in the plant. Due to early spring feeding, 4.7 quintals of additional yield was obtained from 1 hectare of land.

4. In some years, when the growth process in plants begins late in the spring, it faces a period of rising air temperature, the time of transition of developmental phases and the absorption of nutrients decreases. During this period, it is recommended to increase the nitrogen level to 30% instead of 25% of the annual norm in order to increase the accumulation in the plant and the development of generative organs. 5. In early spring, mineral fertilizer suspensions were prepared for areas where wheat grass development was slow, and supplementary feeding accelerated the process of early spring development of plants.

When preparing the solution, 12 kg of amaphos, 6 kg of potassium and 6 kg of nitrate should be dissolved in 300 liters of water and sprinkled on winter wheat stalks using special spraying mechanisms.

6. When the next feeding of winter wheat was carried out at the beginning of the spinning phase, the content of okra in the wheat tube increased by 1.5-2.0% and gluten by 2-4%.

7. Compost prepared for the decomposition of manure and various plant residues, as well as the preparation of juice from them during the period of application of the plant and pouring it through the branches gave a positive result.

8. When rotten manure is mixed with phosphorus and potassium fertilizers and applied to the soil before preparation for planting, the activity of microorganisms in the soil layer of wheat root has improved, their number has increased and the amount of nutrients easily absorbed by plants in the soil has increased.

9. The manure from which the juice is prepared must be rotten, otherwise if the juice is made from pure manure, it will cause the spread of various weeds and some disease-causing fungal spores. In order to prevent such a situation, special ditches should be dug on the farms, and in these ditches or in the case of accumulation, the top should be buried with soil and the manure should be rotted for 4-5 months.

10. In order to protect winter wheat seedlings from losses in autumn, winter and early spring and to obtain the planned harvest, it is preferable to sow in areas with a depth of 2.5-3.0 meters or more and high relief.

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